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Searches for additional scalars with two photons in the final state at CMS *

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Abstract

Although the Higgs boson discovered at the LHC is so far compatible with the Standard Model Higgs boson within the experimental uncertainties, there is still room for extensions of the Standard Model. Some beyond Standard Models, such as the Two Higgs Doublet Model and the Next-to-Minimal Supersymmetric Standard Model, can predict additional Higgs bosons or scalars with rich and interesting phenomenologies. Some latest results of the searches for additional Higgs bosons or scalars with at least two photons included in the final state at CMS are presented. The searches include a search for a standard model-like Higgs boson in the mass range between 70 and 110 GeV in the diphoton final state, for a Higgs boson decaying into scalar(s) with at least one scalar decaying into two photons, and for a high-mass scalar in the exclusive diphoton production via photon-photon fusion with tagged protons. No evidence for the existence of extra scalars is found so far. Some of these searches are performed for the first time based on all LHC data collected by CMS at a center-of-mass energy of 13 TeV.

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1 Introduction

The standard model (SM) [1–3] of particle physics has been very successful in explaining high-energy experimental data. In 2012, a new particle with a mass of ~ 125 GeV was discovered by both ATLAS [4] and CMS [5, 6] experiments at the CERN LHC. The properties of the new particle are so far compatible with those of the SM Higgs boson [7, 8], the quantum of the scalar field postulated by the Brout–Englert–Higgs mechanism [9–11]. Some models for physics beyond the SM (BSM), such as the generalized models containing two Higgs doublets [12, 13], the next-to-minimal supersymmetric model [14–16], and Georgi-Machacek model [17, 18], can provide a Higgs boson that is compatible with the observed 125 GeV boson, and additional Higgs bosons with rich and interesting phenomenologies. So, discovery of additional scalars would be an unequivocal sign of new physics. This paper summarizes CMS latest results of the additional scalar searches with at least two photons included in the final states. The data set utilized is the proton-proton collisions collected with the CMS detector [19] at a center-of-mass energy (\sqrt{s}) of 13 TeV.

2 Search for a standard model-like low-mass Higgs boson in the diphoton final state

The $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ decay channel provides a clean final-state topology that allows the mass of a Higgs boson to be reconstructed with high precision. Several of the BSM models mentioned above permit a significant region of parameter space for enhanced decay rates in the diphoton channel compatible with the constraints in the mass range below 110 GeV extensively explored by CERN LEP collaborations [20] in the context of the search for the SM Higgs boson. A CMS search [21] performed at center-of-mass energies of 8 and 13 TeV in the mass ranges of 70 or $80 < m_{\gamma\gamma} < 110$ GeV reported an excess with respect to the SM prediction, maximal for a mass hypothesis of 95.3 GeV, with a local (global) significance of 2.8 (1.3) standard deviations.

The updated search for a standard model-like Higgs boson decaying into two photons, with same production mechanisms as for the SM Higgs boson and with a natural width much smaller than the detector resolution, in the mass range between 70 and 110 GeV are performed [22]. The analysis uses the data set corresponding to 132.2 fb^{-1} collected during the 2016, 2017 and 2018 LHC running periods, at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. The 2018 version of the high-level trigger (HLT) path used in this analysis was not introduced until after the start of that year’s data taking, resulting in a reduction of the data set by $\sim 5 \text{ fb}^{-1}$.

One of the principal challenges is to suppress the Drell–Yan background with Z bosons decaying to electron pairs that, through misidentification, could mimic two isolated photons. Beside using an electron veto to reject photon candidates geometrically matched to a hit in the pixel detector as used in the prior search [21], the electron veto is reinforced by an additional requirement that no photon candidate is also reconstructed as an electron candidate. To further discriminate against surviving electron pairs from Drell–Yan events, we require that the natural logarithm of the sum of the squares of transverse momenta of all tracks associated with the chosen diphoton vertex satisfies the requirement $\ln(\sum p_T^2/\text{GeV}^2) < 0.016 p_T^{\gamma\gamma}/\text{GeV} + 6.0$, where $p_T^{\gamma\gamma}$ is the transverse momentum of the selected diphoton candidate in each event. As part of this study, the data set of 2016, used in [21], has been reanalyzed with an improved detector calibration. To achieve the best possible sensitivity, the events are separated into classes, including, for the data sets collected in 2017 and 2018, a class requiring the presence of additional jets targeting the VBF production mode. Multivariate analysis (MVA) techniques are used both for photon identification and event classification, and the signal is extracted from the background using a parametric fit to the diphoton mass spectrum in all event classes.

Figure 1 (left) shows the expected and observed 95% confidence level (CL) upper limits on the product of the cross section σ_H and branching fraction \mathcal{B} into two photons, as a function of the mass of an additional SM-like Higgs boson, calculated with respect to the background-only hypothesis,

from the analysis of the combined 2016, 2017, and 2018 data. The observed upper limit ranges from 15 to 73 fb. Figure 1 (right) shows the observed local p -values as a function of the mass of an additional SM-like Higgs boson, calculated with respect to the background-only hypothesis, from the analyses of the data from 2016, 2017, 2018, and their combination. In the case of the combined data set, one excess with approximately 2.9σ local (1.3σ global) significance is observed for a mass hypothesis of 95.4 GeV, where the global significance has been calculated using the method of Ref. [23]. This is the first search for new resonances in the diphoton final state in this mass range based on all CMS data collected at a center-of-mass energy of 13 TeV.

Figure 1: (color online) (Left) Expected and observed exclusion limits (95% CL, in the asymptotic approximation) on the product of the production cross section and branching fraction into two photons for an additional SM-like Higgs boson. The inner and outer bands indicate the regions containing the distribution of limits located within ± 1 and 2σ , respectively, of the expectation under the background-only hypothesis. The corresponding theoretical prediction for the product of the cross section and branching fraction into two photons for an additional SM-like Higgs boson is shown as a solid line with a hatched band, indicating its uncertainty [24]. (Right) The observed local p -values for an additional SM-like Higgs boson as a function of m_H , from the analysis of the data from 2016, 2017, 2018, and their combination.

3 Exotic decays of Higgs boson

3.1 $H \rightarrow Za$ with $Z \rightarrow \ell\ell$ and $a \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$

A search for an exotic decay of the Higgs boson to a Z boson and a light pseudoscalar particle (a), decaying into two leptons ($\ell\ell$) and two photons ($\gamma\gamma$), respectively, is performed based on the data set corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 138 fb^{-1} [25]. The analysis probes pseudoscalar masses m_a between 1 and 30 GeV, leading to two pairs of well-isolated leptons and photons. A boosted decision tree (BDT) classifier is trained to separate the signal from the background, with a unique BDT output obtained for each m_a hypothesis. Events are categorized according to the output of the BDT, separately for each m_a . Finally, simultaneous unbinned maximum likelihood fits of the invariant mass $m_{\ell\ell\gamma\gamma}$ distribution in data are performed, with the mass range $95 < m_{\ell\ell\gamma\gamma} < 180$ GeV and an m_a granularity of 1 GeV in the range 1–30 GeV, to extract the signal.

No significant deviation from the SM expectation is observed. Upper limits at 95% confidence level are set on the product of the Higgs boson production cross section and its branching fraction to two leptons and two photons, as shown in Figure 2 (left). The observed (expected) limits are in the range 1.1–17.8 (1.7–17.9) fb within the probed m_a range. An excess with 2.6σ local (1.3σ global) significance is observed for a mass hypothesis of $m_a = 3$ GeV. Limits on models involving an axion-like particle (ALP), which are formulated as an effective field theory, are also interpreted.

Upper limits at 95% CL are calculated on the Wilson coefficient C_{ZH}^{eff}/Λ [26, 27], as shown in Figure 2 (right), where C_{ZH}^{eff}/Λ is the effective coupling parameter of the Higgs boson, the Z boson, and the ALP, and Λ is the new physics scale. In this interpretation, the ALP is assumed to decay promptly with the branching fraction $\mathcal{B}(a \rightarrow \gamma\gamma) = 100\%$.

Figure 2: (color online) (Left) Expected and observed 95 % CL limits on the product of the production cross section of the Higgs boson into di-photons and di-leptons via a Z boson and a pseudoscalar, $\sigma(pp \rightarrow H) \times \mathcal{B}(H \rightarrow Za \rightarrow \ell\ell\gamma\gamma)$. (Right) Exclusion limits at 95% CL on C_{ZH}^{eff}/Λ , assuming the ALP decays exclusively to a photon pair. The dashed black curve is the expected upper limit, with the one- and two-standard-deviation bands are shown in green and yellow, respectively. The solid black curve is the observed upper limit.

3.2 $H \rightarrow aa/AA \rightarrow \gamma\gamma\gamma\gamma$

Searches for the exotic decay of the Higgs boson to a pair of light pseudoscalars (a) or scalars (A), each of which subsequently decays into a pair of photons, are performed at CMS [28, 29]. The event topology depends on the mass of the pseudoscalar boson being probed, which determines the opening angle between the photons for each pair. Both fully resolved case for the events with four isolated photons in which the angular distance between the photons is greater than 0.2 for both photon pairs, and the boosted case with each particle A decaying promptly to a merged diphoton reconstructed as a single photon-like object, are considered.

For the fully resolved case, the search uses data corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 132.2 fb^{-1} . The analysis probes pseudoscalar bosons with masses (m_a) in the range 15–62 GeV, coming from the Higgs boson decay, which leads to four well-isolated photons in the final state. To improve the sensitivity, a 4γ event classifier BDT, using the identification and kinematic information of the photons and pseudoscalar boson candidates, is trained to separate signal events from background events. An optimized selection on the output of the event classifier is used to define the final signal regions, for the analysis of each m_a . An unbinned maximum likelihood fit of the signal and background models to the observed $m_{\gamma\gamma\gamma\gamma}$ distribution in data in the mass window $110 < m_{\gamma\gamma\gamma\gamma} < 180 \text{ GeV}$, to extract the signal. No significant deviation from the background-only hypothesis is observed. As shown in Figure 3 (left), the observed (expected) limits on the product of the Higgs boson production cross section and branching fraction into four photons, range from 0.80 (1.00) fb for a pseudoscalar boson mass of 15 GeV to 0.26 (0.24) fb for a mass of 62 GeV at 95% CL.

For the boosted case, the search mass range is $0.1 < m_A < 1.2 \text{ GeV}$. The two photons from the A decay will be predominantly reconstructed as one photon-like object (labeled Γ) by the standard CMS photon reconstruction algorithm. This analysis directly measures the invariant mass spectrum of merged diphoton candidates Γ reconstructed in events resembling an SM $H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma$ final state, using data corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 136 fb^{-1} . A novel end-to-end particle reconstruction technique utilizing deep learning algorithms trained directly on ECAL

energy deposits, is developed to measure the invariant mass, m_Γ , of merged diphoton candidates. A sample of events containing two reconstructed photon-like objects ($\Gamma\Gamma$) is selected for analysis. To discriminate the signal events from background, the two-dimensional invariant mass spectrum, m_{Γ_1} vs. m_{Γ_2} , where $m_{\Gamma_{1(2)}}$ is the higher- (lower-) energy reconstructed photon, is used. This is the first search of its kind at CMS and made possible by a novel end-to-end reconstruction technique of merged diphotons. No excess of events above the estimated background is found. As shown in Figure 3 (right), an upper limit on the branching fraction $B(H \rightarrow AA \rightarrow 4\gamma)$ of $(0.9\text{--}3.3) \times 10^{-3}$ is set at 95% CL for masses of A in the range 0.1–1.2 GeV, assuming prompt A decays. These are the current best constraints on $H \rightarrow AA \rightarrow 4\gamma$ in this m_A range.

Figure 3: (color online) (Left) Expected (black dashed curve) and observed (black solid curve with points) 95% CL limits on the product of the production cross section of the Higgs boson and the branching fraction into four photons via a pair of pseudoscalars, $\sigma_H \mathcal{B}(H \rightarrow aa \rightarrow \gamma\gamma\gamma\gamma)$, are shown as a function of m_a . (Right) Observed (black solid curve with points) and median expected (blue dashed curve) 95% CL upper limit on $\mathcal{B}(H \rightarrow aa \rightarrow 4\gamma)$ as a function of m_a for prompt a decays. The green (yellow) bands represent the 68% (95%) expected limit CL intervals. In the right plot, the 95% CL upper limit from the CMS measurement [30] of $\mathcal{B}(H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma)$ is also shown (red band, where the width represents the uncertainty in the measurement).

4 Search for high-mass exclusive diphoton production with tagged protons

A search for high-mass exclusive diphoton production via photon-photon fusion with tagged protons is performed, to probe 4γ Anomalous Quartic Gauge Coupling and search for a pseudo-scalar such as an ALP [31]. The analysis utilizes 102.7 fb^{-1} of data collected by the CMS and TOTEM Precision Proton Spectrometer in the 2016, 2017, and 2018 LHC runs. Events are selected that have two photons with high transverse momenta that are back-to-back in azimuth and with a large diphoton invariant mass. A BDT is used for identification and isolation of photons. To remove the dominant backgrounds, the tagged final state protons from the event are required to match the kinematics of the final state photons. Only events having opposite-side protons within an asymmetric fractional momentum loss between 0.035 and 0.15 (0.18) for the detectors on the negative (positive) side of CMS are considered. One exclusive diphoton candidate is observed for an expected background of 1.1 events. Limits at 95% confidence level are derived for the four-photon anomalous coupling parameters $|\zeta_1| < 0.073 \text{ TeV}^{-4}$ and $|\zeta_2| < 0.15 \text{ TeV}^{-4}$, using an effective field theory. The observed and expected 95% CL in the plane of (ζ_1, ζ_2) are shown in Figure 4 (left). Additionally, upper limits are placed on the production of axion-like particles with coupling strength to photons f^{-1} that varies from 0.03 TeV^{-1} to 1 TeV^{-1} over the mass range from 500 to 2000 GeV.

Figure 4: (color online) (Left) Observed (solid ellipse) and expected (dashed ellipse) exclusion limits at 95% CL on the anomalous coupling parameters ζ_1 and ζ_2 derived from the analysis of high-mass exclusive diphoton events in pp collisions at 13 TeV. (Right) Upper limits at 95% CL on ALP-photon coupling strength as a function of the ALP mass. The shape of the limit curve is determined by the PPS efficiency-times-acceptance curve. The expected limits almost completely overlap with the observed ones.

5 Summary

CMS latest results on the searches for additional scalars with at least two photons included in the final states, are summarized. No evidence for the existence of extra scalars is found so far. In the search for a standard model-like low-mass Higgs boson in the diphoton final state, one excess with approximately 2.9σ local (1.3σ global) significance is observed for a mass hypothesis of 95.4 GeV. In the first LHC analysis of $H \rightarrow Za \rightarrow \ell\ell\gamma\gamma$, an excess with 2.6σ local (1.3σ global) significance is observed for a mass hypothesis of $m_a = 3$ GeV. More data is needed to conclude on the nature of these excesses. Both fully resolved and boosted cases of $H \rightarrow aa/AA \rightarrow \gamma\gamma\gamma\gamma$ were performed by CMS for the first time. The boosted $H \rightarrow AA \rightarrow \gamma\gamma\gamma\gamma$ result gives the best constraints for this decay mode in the studied mass range. For the search for high-mass exclusive diphoton production with tagged protons, it gives the strongest limits on ALP production in the search range.

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